

D1.4 Status Report

Prepared by: forScience in collaboration with
ICEBERG WP1 partners

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Table of Contents

Version History	1
Deliverable Information	1
Table of Contents	2
List of Figures	4
List of Tables	4
Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
1 Introduction	7
2 Overview of Work Package 1	7
2.1 General description	7
2.2 WP1 partners	8
2.3 Objectives	9
3 Explanation of work carried out per task	11
3.1 Task 1.1 Arctic ship traffic pollutants and lower food web effects	11
3.1.1 Task overview	11
3.1.2 Explanation of work carried out	12
3.1.3 Preliminary findings	13
3.2 Task 1.2 Arctic antibiotic resistome in the plastisphere	16
3.2.1 Task overview	16
3.2.2 Explanation of work carried out	16
3.2.3 Preliminary findings	17
3.3 Task 1.3 Chemical contaminants in snow and ice	17
3.3.1 Task overview	17
3.3.2 Explanation of work carried out	18
3.3.3 Preliminary findings	19
3.4 Task 1.4 Coastal (1.4a) and open ocean pollution (1.4b)	19
3.4.1 Task overview	19
3.4.2 Explanation of work carried out	20
3.4.3 Preliminary findings	21
3.5 Task 1.5 Sediment sampling and analysis	21
3.5.1 Task overview	21
3.5.2 Explanation of work carried out	21
3.5.3 Preliminary findings	22
3.6 Task 1.6 Pollution assessment	23
3.6.1 Task overview	23
3.6.2 Explanation of work carried out	23
3.6.3 Preliminary findings	24
3.7 Task 1.7 Incubation experiments	24
3.7.1 Task overview	24

- 3.7.2 Explanation of work carried out24
- 3.7.3 Preliminary findings.....25
- 3.8 Task 1.8 Stranded Marine Litter25
 - 3.8.1 Task overview.....25
 - 3.8.2 Explanation of work carried out26
 - 3.8.3 Preliminary findings.....27
- 3.9 Task 1.9 Monitoring of litter dynamics29
 - 3.9.1 Task overview.....29
 - 3.9.2 Explanation of work carried out29
 - 3.9.3 Preliminary findings.....29
- 3.10 Task 1.10 Heavy metal contamination31
 - 3.10.1 Task overview.....31
 - 3.10.2 Explanation of work carried out31
 - 3.10.3 Preliminary findings.....32
- 3.11 Task 1.11 Integration/synthesis of results, report writing33
 - 3.11.1 Task overview.....33
 - 3.11.2 Explanation of work carried out33
 - 3.11.3 Preliminary findings.....33

List of Figures

Figure 1. WP1 tasks and their respective study areas.....	8
Figure 2. Release sites and advection pathways of particle tracking experiments.....	12
Figure 3. Marine traffic trends and patterns in the study area.....	14
Figure 4. Ship traffic in the Nordic Seas in 2022 for all ship types combined.....	15
Figure 5. Station overview of the Fram Strait expeditions.....	17
Figure 6. Snow pit sampling in the Brøgger glacier, Svalbard, April 2024.....	18
Figure 7. Snow pit sampling sites around Kongsfjorden, Svalbard.....	19
Figure 8. Image of the study region and mooring line configuration.....	20
Figure 9. Map of the study region in northern Svalbard.....	22
Figure 10. Example of geochemistry data measured in surface sediments (2023).....	23
Figure 11. Set-up of an incubation experiment.....	25
Figure 12. Task 1.8 study area.....	26
Figure 13. Time-lapse camera in Svalbard.....	30
Figure 14. Location of the time-lapse camera in Svalbard.....	30
Figure 15. Soil and freshwater sampling spots in Svalbard.....	31
Figure 16. Soil sampling conducted in July 2024.....	32
Figure 17. Freshwater sampling conducted in July 2024.....	32

List of Tables

Table 1. WP1 objectives and summary of progress.....	10
Table 2. WP1 Gantt Chart.....	11
Table 3. Type of data collected as part of the extended marine litter analysis (Deep Dive).....	28

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AAS	Atomic Absorption Spectrometry
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ARG	Antibiotic Resistance Genes
ASTD	Arctic Ship Traffic Data(base)
BFR	Brominated Flame Retardants
BP	Bisphenol
BPA	Bisphenol-A
BTEX	Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzenes, Xylene
BTH	Benzothiazoles
CDOM	Colored Dissolved Organic Matter
CH4	Methane
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6
CO	Carbon Monoxide
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, Depth
DCM	Deep Chlorophyll Maximum
DMS	Dimethyl Sulfide
EC	Emerging Contaminant
EG	East Greenland
FOCI	Flexible Ocean and Climate Infrastructure
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
HDPE	High-density Polyethylene
HG	LTER-HAUSGARTEN: Long-Term Ecological Research observatory HAUSGARTEN, constitutes a network of 21 permanent sampling sites.
HPLC - MS/MS	High Performance Liquid Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry
IC	Ion Chromatography
ICP MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
MLCs	Micro-litter Compounds
MPs	Microplastics
NMVOC	Non-methane Volatile Organic Carbon
OCP	Organochlorine Pesticides
OPPLA	Optimality-based Plankton Ecosystem Model
PAHs	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
PAME	Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (Arctic Council Working Group)
PBB	Polybrominated Biphenyls
PBDE	Polybrominated Diphenyl Ethers

PCBs	Polychlorinated Biphenyls
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
POPs	Persistent Organic Pollutants
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
SV	Svalbard
UV	Ultraviolet Radiation

1 Introduction

The purpose of Deliverable 1.4: Status report is to provide a comprehensive, joint update on the progress of Work Package 1 (WP1) during the first 14 months of the project (M1–M14). The report demonstrates that WP1 is progressing according to plan, with tasks on track to meet the stated objectives. It provides task overviews, explains the work carried out thus far and outlines preliminary findings where applicable. Through this deliverable, the WP1 partners aim to make certain that all activities within WP1 are aligned with project goals and timelines, and to confirm readiness for the next phase of fieldwork.

2 Overview of Work Package 1

2.1 General description

WP1 aims to advance the scientific understanding of the sources, distributions and impacts of pollution in the European Arctic. Two major types of pollutants are distinguished:

1. **Particulate pollutants:** these pollutants, which include for example macro- and microplastics, are exclusively distributed via advection. They are characterised by their non-natural origin, high persistence, and significant impact on higher trophic levels, including fish and mammals. Additionally, they serve as carriers for bacteria.
2. **Dissolved and suspended pollutants:** these pollutants disperse through molecular and turbulent diffusion, as well as advection. Examples include wastewater discharges and pollutants resulting from the melting of the terrestrial cryosphere. This category encompasses a wide range of substances, including naturally occurring labile and semi-labile organic compounds, trace metals, and persistent organic pollutants (POPs) of anthropogenic origin.

A key aspect that WP1 investigates is plankton ecosystem response to various pollutants, considering different types, intensities, and frequencies of ship discharges and pollutant releases in relation to climatic and cryospheric changes. WP1 considers these microbial investigations critical to the One Health approach, as these organisms are the base of the food chain. Other WPs will investigate the higher trophic levels that feed off these microbial organisms. To achieve its objectives, WP1 employs a multidisciplinary approach that combines field analyses, laboratory experiments, statistical methods, and model simulations.

WP1 contains eleven separate tasks, all of which will be discussed in Section 3: Explanation of work carried out per task. The primary study area for WP1 is Svalbard and the surrounding waters, including the Fram Strait (Figure 1), but samples are planned to be collected also in southern Greenland and northern Iceland.

Figure 1. WP1 tasks and their respective study areas

Figure credit: B. Józwiak & A. Nawrot, Fundacja forScience. Made with Natural Earth

2.2 WP1 partners

WP1 is composed of five partners: one non-governmental organisation (NGO), one university, and three research institutions, with a total 27 participants based in Poland, Germany, Italy, and France. Each partner plays a crucial role in the work package, contributing essential expertise.

1. Fundacja forScience

- Short name: forScience
- Country: Poland
- Role in WP1: **WP1 lead**; **Task 1.8:** Stranded marine litter; **T1.10:** Heavy metal contamination; **T1.11:** Integration/synthesis of results, report writing.
- Expertise: Fundacja forScience provides expertise on the quality, quantity, distribution and accumulation rate of marine litter in remote areas of Svalbard, as well as extensive experience in Arctic fieldwork and logistics. It employs a variety of techniques for environmental sample collection and collaborates within its strong professional research network to provide thorough data analyses and interpretations.

2. Helmholtz-Zentrum Für Ozeanforschung Kiel

- Short name: GEOMAR
- Country: Germany

- Role in WP1: **WP1 co-lead; Tasks 1.1:** Arctic ship traffic pollutants and lower trophic food web effects; **T1.2:** Arctic Ocean antibiotic resistome in the plastisphere; **T1.6:** Pollution assessment; **T1.7:** Incubation experiments.
- Expertise: GEOMAR will use a variety of techniques to quantitatively and qualitatively characterise pollutants and their impacts in the European Arctic, including numerical ecosystem models, cutting-edge microbiological and molecular biology techniques, manipulation experiments, and mass spectrometry. GEOMAR's access to research ships provides an additional benefit to the project, as the three field sites can be complemented by open ocean measurements made by GEOMAR team members.

3. Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche

- Short name: ISP-CNR
- Country: Italy
- Role in WP1: **T1.3:** Chemical contaminants in snow and ice; **T1.4:** Coastal (1.4a) and open ocean (1.4b) pollution; **T1.5:** Sediment sampling and analysis.
- Expertise: ISP-CNR brings expertise on both cryosphere and marine domains as well as the analytical competence to quantify a wide range of contaminants in different matrices (ice and sediments).

4. Christian-Albrechts-Universitaet Zu Kiel

- Short name: CAU
- Country: Germany
- Role in WP1: **T1.9:** Monitoring of litter dynamics.
- Expertise: CAU provides expertise in remote sensing, set-up of time-lapse cameras, and machine learning to automatically detect marine beach litter.

5. Ecole Nationale Veterinaire, Agroalimentaire Et De L'alimentation Nantes Atlantique

- Short name: ONIRIS
- Country: France
- Role in WP1: **T1.3:** Chemical contaminants in snow and ice; **T1.4:** Coastal (1.4a) and open ocean (1.4b) pollution; **T1.5:** Sediment sampling and analysis.
- Expertise: ONIRIS brings expertise in analytical chemistry, characterisation of a range of organic pollutants (PCBs, PFASs, flame retardants, organochlorine pesticides) in various environmental matrices (snow, sediments) using chromatographic-mass spectrometric methods.

2.3 Objectives

The ICEBERG project has a two-fold aim:

- to comprehensively assess sources, types, distributions and impacts of human and climate change-induced pollution on ecosystems and communities in the European Arctic land-ocean continuum using a One Health approach, and
- to develop strategies for enhancing community-led resilience and adaptation, as well as pollution-control governance and policy recommendations.

WP1 contributes to this aim by collecting and analysing samples from the field, performing experiments in the field and at home institutes, and analysing model runs (Table 1).

Table 1. WP1 objectives and summary of progress

Objectives	Summary of progress
1) Advance the scientific understanding of the sources, distributions, and impacts of pollution in the European Arctic.	WP1 has successfully completed the majority of planned fieldwork and secured snow, sediment, water and plastic samples for analysis. Analytical tasks have been allocated and shared strategies have been developed to ensure result comparability. Some laboratory analyses have already been completed, and others are in progress. The first set of quantitative, qualitative and distributional data on marine litter pollution in the near shore terrestrial environment of the Arctic has been obtained. In-depth litter data analysis is in progress. Modelling work to assess the impact of ship disposals is in progress. The first round of incubation experiments has been completed.
2) Develop model simulations of key aspects such as plankton ecosystem responses to ship disposals, release of pollutants to the ocean in response to climatic and cryospheric changes, and marine and coastal food web forecasting of food safety (in collaboration with WP2).	With access to PAME's (Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment workgroup) Arctic Ship Traffic Database (ASTD) granted in August 2024, work has started on the identification of the most prominent shipping routes with considerable atmospheric and wastewater emissions. Particle tracking experiments on ocean circulation model data revealed typical transport pathways. Work is currently underway to synthesise and integrate the complex information gathered from ASTD and the transport pathways into a modelling framework.
3) Assess toxicological impact of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants, if relevant (PFAS), on ecosystem and human health (in collaboration with WP2).	Environmental samples (snow, sediments) from Svalbard have been collected for the One Health study focusing on the environment- food-health continuum. Arctic waters from the Fram Strait have been obtained to perform experiments targeting the base of the oceanic food chain and their ecosystem services.
4) Determine the role of microplastic, associated antibiotic resistant bacteria and antibiotic resistance genes, on ecosystem and human health.	Field sampling in the Fram Strait was successfully completed in the summer of 2024. In addition, a plastic incubation experiment with surface water collected close to Svalbard, using seven different polymers, was carried out during the RV Polarstern cruise PS143-1/2. The processing of these samples has started and is progressing. During PS143, surface water off East Greenland (EG) marine stations (Figure 5) was collected and used for incubation experiments at GEOMAR (Task 1.7). In collaboration with ISP-CNR, the same polymers were deployed at two moorings in Kongsfjorden and the Fram Strait, with recovery scheduled for May/June 2025.

3 Explanation of work carried out per task

The following section outlines the work that has been done with respect to the first 14 months of the project and directly relating to the first fieldwork period (Table 2).

Table 2. WP1 Gantt Chart: Timeline for WP1 during the months 1 to 14. Cells marked in blue represent active months, while cells marked in green indicate months with fieldwork

Task	Lead	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14
1.1	GEOMAR				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.2	GEOMAR	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.3	CNR, ONIRIS	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.4	CNR, ONIRIS	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.5	CNR, ONIRIS	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.6	GEOMAR	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.7	GEOMAR						█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.8	FORSCIENCE	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.9	CAU	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.10	FORSCIENCE					█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
1.11	FORSCIENCE												█	█	█

3.1 Task 1.1 Arctic ship traffic pollutants and lower food web effects

Lead: GEOMAR; M4–M23

3.1.1 Task overview

Growing economic interests, increasing tourism and a decreasing sea-ice cover contribute to increasing shipping activities and changing shipping routes in the Arctic. In Task 1.1, GEOMAR researchers develop model simulations to investigate plankton ecosystem responses to pollutant disposals by marine traffic. The modelling framework combines three major concepts: 1) an optimality-based ecosystem model to simulate the plankton in one-dimensional (1D) vertical water columns; 2) particle tracking simulations to identify typical transport pathways in a fully-coupled Earth system model, providing the physical model forcing for the 1D ecosystem model along the ensemble of Lagrangian trajectories (pathways of surface water mass transport along ocean currents); 3) emission estimates of various ship-associated pollutant types from Arctic Ship Traffic Data (ASTD).

The modelling approach allows the assessment of potential impacts on the lower food web at three case study sites (Iceland, Greenland and Svalbard) caused by local and down-stream contamination with ship discharge. Furthermore, the effects of changes in marine traffic intensity and routes on the carbonate system and the mass flux of Carbon, Nitrogen, and Phosphorus through the planktonic ecosystem, including primary productivity and export, can be investigated. Considering projections of increasing ocean temperatures and stratification based

on the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6 (CMIP6)¹ scenarios SSP1 (sustainable pathway) and SSP3 (regional rivalry), combined with increased marine traffic (ASTD-derived trends), can provide an estimate of food web and mass flux impacts in a changing Arctic.

3.1.2 Explanation of work carried out

GEOMAR designed a modelling approach for combining the Optimality-based Plankton Ecosystem Model OPPLA² with the physical environment derived from a fully coupled (ocean, atmosphere, and land), model of the Flexible Ocean and Climate Infrastructure (FOCI)³, while considering a Lagrangian perspective.

In preliminary experiments, GEOMAR researchers have successfully extracted ensembles of Lagrangian trajectories to and from the case study sites north of Iceland, south of Greenland, and west of Svalbard (Figure 2a) in the Fram Strait from FOCI simulation results. Particle tracking experiments were conducted using the OceanParcels toolbox, simulating the advection of 100 particles for 180 days upstream to and downstream from each case study site (Figure 2b). The physical environment, including temperature and salinity profiles, as well as solar radiation and wind speed at the surface, was extracted along these trajectories. The particle tracking analysis was initially limited to 2020 for development and concept testing, with ongoing works to expand it to the period 2015-2022.

Figure 2. Release sites and advection pathways of particle tracking experiments

100 virtual particles were released at each case study site (a). The particle advection (b) was tracked for 180 days downstream (forward in time; darker colours) and upstream (backward in time; lighter colours) from each site (Svalbard=red, Iceland=blue, Greenland=yellow). Figure credit: V. Lampe, GEOMAR

¹ Eyring, V., Bony, S., Meehl, G. A., Senior, C. A., Stevens, B., Stouffer, R. J., & Taylor, K. E. (2016). Overview of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(5), 1937–1958. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016>

² Pahlow, M. (2023). OPPLA (Optimality-based plankton ecosystem model). Open Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8289208. <https://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/60886/>

³ Matthes, K., Biastoch, A., Wahl, S., Harlaß, J., Martin, T., Brücher, T., Drews, A., Ehlert, D., Getzlaff, K., Krüger, F., Rath, W., Scheinert, M., Schwarzkopf, F. U., Bayr, T., Schmidt, H., & Park, W. (2020). The Flexible Ocean and Climate Infrastructure version 1 (FOCI1): Mean state and variability. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 13(6), 2533–2568. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-2533-2020>

GEOMAR was granted access to PAME's ASTD in August 2024. From these highly detailed and large datasets based on the Automatic Identification System (AIS), a pipeline was created to identify major routes of marine traffic and to calculate atmospheric and wastewater emissions for different ship types along these routes. With more than 400 GB of tabular data consisting of approximately 1.5×10^9 individual observations, the analyses of ASTD turned out to be computationally expensive and require a large amount of hard disk storage. Therefore, the decision was made to proceed with the analyses on a High-Performance Computing cluster (Kiel University's NESH system). Analyses for three representative years (2015, 2020, 2022) were successfully completed, with ongoing works to cover the entire 2015-2022 period. To integrate the insights drawn from ASTD into a modelling framework, a statistical approach was chosen that aggregates monthly garbage, wastewater (blackwater, greywater, and bilgewater) as well as atmospheric (CO, CO₂, SO₂, CH₄, NMVOC (non-methane volatile organic carbon)) ship emissions over the approximately 0.5 x 0.5° grid of the physical model. The projecting of the emission data from ASTD to the physical model grid used will facilitate their integration into the Lagrangian modelling framework.

Works on integrating the OPPLA ecosystem model with the physical forcing along Lagrangian trajectories and ship depositions derived from ASTD are ongoing.

3.1.3 Preliminary findings

Preliminary analyses of ASTD reveal a general increase of marine activity in the Nordic Seas between 2015-2022, in terms of the number of individual ships observed in the area (Figure 3a). As expected, ship trafficking is found to be generally higher during summer months compared to the winter. The composition of ship types, shown exemplary for 2022 in Figure 3b, appeared relatively stable throughout the year, although the number of cruise ships increased during these summer months (Jun-Aug). As different ship types have different emission profiles, seasonal changes in the vessel composition can therefore drive differences in seasonal emission (ocean disposal) patterns, in addition to changes in the general maritime activity. In 2022, and within the area of interest, the deposition of greywater (Figure 3d; from showers and sinks), blackwater (Figure 3e; toilets and kitchen sinks, higher contamination), and garbage (Figure 3f) was largely driven by passenger ships and cruise ships, despite both types only contributing a small fraction of the total number of ships observed. The increase in cruise ship numbers during the summer caused a noticeable peak in wastewater and garbage emissions.

In addition to the temporal patterns, marine traffic in 2022 was not spread evenly across the region but focused on shipping routes and along coastlines, specifically near ports (Figure 4a). The traffic density, here expressed as total navigated distance within each model grid cell per year, was especially high along the Norwegian coast, around Iceland, southwestern Greenland, and west of Svalbard, as well as on the direct paths between these locations. Furthermore, the regions of activity differed between ship types. For example, fishing vessels (Figure 4b) operated in a broad band along coastlines and islands, largely reflecting their movements between their fishing grounds and home harbours. In contrast, cruise ships (Figure 4c) primarily operated closer to the coasts and along straight and long segments connecting ports, which reflects typical round-trip journeys.

Figure 3. Marine traffic trends and patterns in the study area

Study area is presented in (c). The number of individual ships observed per month in three different years (a) is broken down by ship types for 2022 in (b). Respective emissions of greywater (d), blackwater (e), and garbage (f) are also broken down by ship type for 2022. The colour legend given in (g) thus applies to b and d-f. Figure credit: V. Lampe, GEOMAR. Data Source: ASTD/PAME

Figure 4. Ship traffic in the Nordic Seas in 2022 for all ship types combined

(a), fishing vessels (b), and cruise ships (c). The total navigated distance per gridcell per year serves as an indicator of shipping activity. Note, the colour scale ranges differ. Figure credit: V. Lampe, GEOMAR. Raw data source: ASTD/PAME

3.2 Task 1.2 Arctic antibiotic resistome in the plastisphere

Lead: GEOMAR; M1–M24

3.2.1 Task overview

Antibiotics are among the most essential treatments for bacterial-mediated infectious diseases, globally the second-leading cause of death. However, the prevalence of antibiotic resistance is increasing, posing a significant public health threat. Antibiotic-resistant bacteria and their resistome disperse through different routes in the environment, such as rivers and oceans. Despite the evident risk that marine microbes evolve resistance mechanisms and facilitate the horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) to human-associated bacteria, little is known about the role of plastic pollution, particularly nano- and microplastics in these processes. In Task 1.2, GEOMAR researchers characterise the microbial community structure and function associated with polymers and Arctic seawater, using 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, metagenomics, and metatranscriptomics. This task comprises identifying potential pathogens and estimating the relative proportions of ARGs in metagenomes and metatranscriptomes. Collectively, these data will allow GEOMAR to estimate the role of microplastic and polymer types as vectors contributing to the spreading of antibiotic resistance across the Arctic Ocean.

3.2.2 Explanation of work carried out

GEOMAR researchers conducted sampling of plastic particles in the Fram Strait during the RV POLARSTERN cruises PS143-1/2 (June to August 2024) for subsequent extraction of total DNA to determine the bacterial community composition on plastic particles of different size classes. For determining Arctic bacterioplankton function (RNAmetaT), GEOMAR collected seawater samples at several stations from the surface, deep chlorophyll-a (DCM), 50 m, and 100 m depths, samples were preserved with RNALater, flash-frozen, and stored at -80°C until further processing in the home laboratory (Figure 5). To investigate the influence of anthropogenic pollution on the microbial community and biogeochemistry, attempts were made to collect naturally occurring microplastic particles (> 300 µm) at selected stations by filtering seawater, which was continuously drawn from the ship's underway system at ~10 m below the surface. However, this exhaustive sampling effort did not result in a sufficient amount of naturally occurring microplastic for genomic analysis. Therefore, an incubation experiment was conducted during PS143 with water from 10 m depth collected with the CTD rosette. A total of 24 glass jars were filled with one litre of seawater each, and seven different types of plastic were incubated in triplicates at 4°C. The experiment was run for several weeks (~40 days) and completed during the cruise. In addition, stainless-steel plates that can hold up to 36 plastic discs were designed and manufactured. These plates were equipped with the same plastic mentioned above and attached to two moorings in Kongsfjorden and one in the Fram Strait in September 2024 (see Task 1.4 and Figure 8). Recovery of these plates is scheduled to take place between July and September 2025. Metatranscriptomic and 16S amplicon sequencing will be used to investigate the biodiversity and function of plastic-associated bacteria, focusing on potential pathogens and their resistome. This information will be used to identify potential pathogens in the field samples.

Figure 5. Station overview of the Fram Strait expeditions

PS143 cruises 1 (a) and 2 (b), covering 88 and 78 discrete seawater samples, respectively, from four depth layers (10 m, deep chlorophyll-*a*, 50 m, and 100 m depth). A subset of these samples from Svalbard (SV), LTER-HAUSGARTEN (HG), and East Greenland (EG) stations will be used for further processing. Figure credit: B. Pontiller, GEOMAR

3.2.3 Preliminary findings

No preliminary results are available at this point.

3.3 Task 1.3 Chemical contaminants in snow and ice

Lead: ISP-CNR, ONIRIS; M1–M24

3.3.1 Task overview

The Arctic's seemingly clean snow cover acts as a crucial archive, recording the deposition of pollutants transported over vast distances. Task 1.3 investigates emerging contaminants (ECs) in the Arctic snow and ice matrices, looking for clues of long-range transport of these substances. ISP-CNR focuses on bisphenol (BPs), benzothiazoles (BTHs), personal care products (fragrances and UV filters), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Moreover, ONIRIS investigates perfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS). The overarching goal is to quantify the concentrations of ECs, pinpoint their sources and reconstruct the type of transport they undergo to better understand their impact and their long-range transport in the remote area of the Svalbard Archipelago.

Figure 6. Snow pit sampling in the Brøgger glacier, Svalbard, April 2024

Photo credit: E. Barbaro, CNR

3.3.2 Explanation of work carried out

To ensure timely results and meet project goals, ISP-CNR utilised snow samples already collected (2021, 2022, and 2023) and samples collected during the field campaign in 2024. A total of 455 snow samples collected in three glaciers of Brøgger Peninsula (Svalbard) during four consecutive years (2021, 2022, 2023 and 2024) were successfully processed (Figure 6). For each glacier, a snow pit was dug, and the samples were collected with 10-cm resolution along the seasonal snowpack (Figure 7). In each sample, thirteen bisphenols and eight benzothiazoles were analysed using HPLC-MS/MS techniques. The analysis is complete, and data elaboration is in progress. Preliminary elaboration confirmed the occurrence of three bisphenols and eight benzothiazoles, with specific profile along the depth of the glacier. The analysis of Personal Care Products, PAHs, and PFAS is still ongoing, which is why there are no preliminary data yet.

Figure 7. Snow pit sampling sites around Kongsfjorden, Svalbard

See Figure 1 for the location of the study area in Svalbard. Figure credit: T. Tesi, CNR

3.3.3 Preliminary findings

For benzothiazoles, preliminary data suggest an increasing trend in the total BTHs flow (i.e. accumulation) from 2021 to 2024. In particular, the sampling location with the highest presence of benzothiazoles seems to be the snow pit from the Midtre Lovénbreen 2024. As far as bisphenols are concerned, the preliminary data show that in all three of the considered fluxes, the highest levels were recorded in the years 2021 and 2023, while the lowest were observed in 2024. In particular, the highest flux concentrations appear to have been recorded in Kongsvegen, which is the only tidewater glacier sampled among the different sites.

3.4 Task 1.4 Coastal (1.4a) and open ocean pollution (1.4b)

Lead: ISP-CNR, ONIRIS; M1–M24

3.4.1 Task overview

The Arctic's delicate food web is increasingly threatened by the pervasive presence of microplastics and micro-litter compounds. Zooplankton, a crucial link in this chain, are particularly vulnerable to ingesting these pollutants. Task 1.4 focuses on qualitative and quantitative analyses of small microplastics (MPs) and micro-litter compounds (MLCs) in the zooplanktonic food-web chain in coastal (Task 1.4a) and open ocean (Task 1.4b). The main goals are: 1) characterise the ingested MPs and MLCs by selected taxa to understand how MPs reflect different feeding mechanisms, 2) compare different coastal sites and coastal-open ocean areas to highlight pollution pathways and 3) identify potential bioindicators for MPs and MLCs pollution in high-Arctic ecosystems.

3.4.2 Explanation of work carried out

Permanent marine observatories, such as mooring lines, are invaluable tools for long-term zooplankton studies. These installations provide continuous, high-resolution data on environmental parameters (like temperature, salinity, and current flow) which directly influence zooplankton distribution and behaviour. By integrating these physical data with zooplankton sampling done with sediment traps (Figure 8), ISP-CNR track seasonal changes, understand population dynamics, and assess the impact of environmental shifts as well as the influence of plastic pollution. ISP-CNR selected sediment trap samples from three mooring lines deployed in Kongsfjorden (MDI and MAP) and Krossfjorden (KIM), Svalbard, matching the same years as the snow samples (2021-2022) (Figure 8) (Task 1.4a). To investigate open-ocean microplastic pollution and the transfer through the food-chain, samples were also selected from an open-ocean mooring line (Fram Strait) collected in 2022-2023 (Task 1.4b). Due to the time-consuming nature of the analyses, focus was initially on quantifying the number of species (taxonomy sorting) and then measured small MPs and MLCs in four commonly found species within Kongsfjorden-Krossfjorden fjords. For the open water samples, a similar strategy was employed, with four species from the intermediate depth environment identified and sorted for subsequent MPs and MLCs analyses. In total, ISP-CNR successfully identified and sorted four species per site for small MPs and MLCs analyses in both the coastal region and the open water. Currently, the chemical digestion for quali-quantitative analyses of ingested MPs and MLCs is ongoing.

Figure 8. Image of the study region and mooring line configuration

See Figure 1 for the region's location in Svalbard. The location of the three mooring lines (KIM, MDI and MAP) is shown as filled orange circles (a). An example of mooring line (MAP) configuration is shown (b), with several instruments used to measure physical property of the water column while the sediment trap collects the zooplankton as swimmers in the water column. Note: the stainless-steel plate containing plastic discs for Task 1.2 incubation experiment. Figure credit: G. Ingresso, CNR

3.4.3 Preliminary findings

Preliminary data on taxonomic sorting suggest the occurrences of three common groups (i.e., *Calanus glacialis*, *Metridia longa* and *Themisto abyssorum*) between Fram Strait, Krossfjorden and Kongsfjorden, while appendicularians of the species *Oikopleura (Vexillaria) vanhoeffeni* have been replaced by ostracods of the Tribù Conchoecini in the Fram Strait area. First results on *C. glacialis* collected in Krossfjorden show the ingestion of 29 small MPs, 36 MLCs and seven tire-road wear particles, the latter derived from tyre degradation, with an average number of particles for a specimen ranging between 70 and 80.

3.5 Task 1.5 Sediment sampling and analysis

Lead: ISP-CNR, ONIRIS; M1–M24

3.5.1 Task overview

Arctic marine sediments act as a receptor, preserving a historical record of environmental changes in remote regions, including pollutant inputs. Task 1.5 focuses on analysing pollutant concentrations in sediments collected from northern Svalbard (Krossfjorden and Kongsfjorden) across different sedimentological contexts, such as tidewater and land-terminating glaciers. A key objective of Task 1.5 is to differentiate between long-range and local pollutant transport. Long-range transport occurs primarily through the influx of Atlantic Water, which can carry pollutants from distant sources over large spatial scales and atmospheric deposition driven by inputs from glaciers and snowmelt (Task 1.3). In contrast, local input derives from direct anthropogenic sources from settlements. Notably, meltwater from tidewater glaciers and land-terminating glaciers may release contaminants accumulated over time, while the Ny-Ålesund International Research Station and other human activities in the region contribute additional local sources of pollution. By investigating pollutant distribution across various sites and sedimentological contexts, ISP-CNR aim to better understand the relative importance of long-range atmospheric and oceanic transport versus local environmental and anthropogenic inputs in shaping pollutant deposition in Svalbard's marine fjords.

3.5.2 Explanation of work carried out

Surface sediments (surface seabed) are collected from strategic locations to align with the study sites of Task 1.3 and Task 1.4. This approach allows us to integrate information from snow and the water column. Our work follows two timeframes: 1) contemporary and 2) historical reconstruction. The former is achieved using surface sediments (Figure 10), while the latter relies on a sediment core that enables us to analyse past environmental conditions (Figure 9). In 2023 and 2024, ISP-CNR collected 90 and 69 surface sediment samples, respectively, from Kongsfjorden and Krossfjorden. On these samples, bulk measurements were conducted, such as total organic carbon analysis (e.g., Figure 10), and the concentrations of various contaminants are planned to be measured. These include fragrances (synthetic or natural compounds used for scent), UV filters (chemicals that block or absorb UV radiation), bisphenols (a group of additives used in plastics and epoxy resins, including Bisphenol A (BPA)), benzothiazoles (used in rubber manufacturing and as a corrosion inhibitor), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs, formerly used in industrial and electronic products), polybrominated diphenyl ethers and other brominated flame retardants (PBDEs and PBBs, used in electronic products), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS, used in various industrial and personal care products as well as in food contact materials), and microplastics (particles less than 5 mm in size). So far, a set of analyses have been completed for the 2023 surface sediment samples, including bulk measurements, PFAS, BFRs, and PBDEs. Additionally, analytical methods for UV filters, BPA, and benzothiazoles have been tested and validated. To explore how the contamination changed over time during the last centuries, a sediment core already available and collected in 2021 was used, which has been stored at 4°C at the ISP-CNR core repository. The core was

subsampled at 1-cm intervals, an age-depth model was developed for the last 200 years, and analyses are currently ongoing.

Figure 9. Map of the study region in northern Svalbard

Map shows the surface sediments collected in 2023 (red filled circles) and 2024 (green filled circles). Blue filled circle displays the location of a sediment core collected off Ny-Ålesund (yellow filled circle). See Figure 1 for the location of the study area in Svalbard. Figure credit: T. Tesi, CNR

3.5.3 Preliminary findings

Preliminary results indicate that, despite the relatively small study area, surface sediments in Kongsfjorden show significant variations in the concentrations of the quantified compounds, particularly PFAS. The lowest concentrations were observed near the large tidewater glaciers (Kongsvegen and Kronebreen), while the highest concentrations were found in front of the Brøgger land terminal glacier. This region is also influenced by local sources and the inflow of Atlantic Water into the fjord. Additional analyses at the fjord entrance and in nearby Krossfjorden will help us better understand the relative contributions of Atlantic Water, snowmelt, and local inputs.

Figure 10. Example of geochemistry data measured in surface sediments (2023)

The figure shows the different concentration of organic carbon in surface sediments, highlighting a large variability despite the small domain. This reflects different environmental conditions, in particular the influence of large tide-water glaciers like Kronebreen and Kongsvegen. Figure credit: T. Tesi, CNR

3.6 Task 1.6 Pollution assessment

Lead: GEOMAR, Contributors: ISP-CNR, forScience; M1–M24

3.6.1 Task overview

The aim of the task is to obtain (from ISP-CNR, forScience) and collect samples (GEOMAR) for the analysis of a variety of liquid, gaseous and particulate pollutants. Samples will include aerosols collected on filters, ambient air (gas) samples, effluent from ships, wastewater, freshwater/cryosphere discharge, and macro-, micro-, and nanoplastics. Analyses will include PAHs, heavy metals, gases, pH, and isotopes. The objective is to determine the relevance of some of these pollutant sources for direct and indirect microbial effects.

3.6.2 Explanation of work carried out

All partners in WP1 collected information about potential analyses and field sites to create a pollution assessment spreadsheet. The pollution assessment spreadsheet mainly consists of pollutants which can be analysed by every partner in WP1. One goal is to form the basis to define what kind of pollutants GEOMAR is able to/should monitor in their incubation experiments (Task 1.7). A second goal is to catalogue pollutants measured over all field sites during the first two years of the project. During the first fieldwork campaign in the summer of 2024, various trace metal soil and freshwater samples were taken by Fundacja forScience in Svalbard. Measurements of different

kinds of pollutants carried out by all partners during the first fieldwork campaign will be added to the pollution assessment spreadsheet when available (e.g. Tasks 1.3, 1.4, 1.5). Literature and database searches will be performed to augment this information.

3.6.3 Preliminary findings

No preliminary results are available at this point.

3.7 Task 1.7 Incubation experiments

Lead: GEOMAR, Contributors: ISP-CNR, forScience; M1–M24

3.7.1 Task overview

The goal of this task is to perform incubation experiments of natural Arctic waters to investigate the influence of different pollutants (collected in Task 1.6) on biogeochemical processes in the surface ocean. This includes influences on microbes (base of the food chain) and the (microbial) biogenic influence on climate-active trace gases such as dimethyl sulfide (DMS), isoprene, carbonyl sulfide, and carbon disulfide. These gases are naturally produced and consumed in the surface through biologically mediated processes and once in the atmosphere form aerosols that interact with radiation, providing background climate impacts. Changes in microbiological communities in the surface ocean due to increasing pollutant load will change the cycling of these important trace gases, which may have non-negligible climate impacts. Findings from this task will be given to the team implementing Task 1.1 (GEO-BM) for incorporation into models. Information of in-situ surface microbial community composition will be provided from Task 1.2.

3.7.2 Explanation of work carried out

To understand pollution-induced biogenic climate-active trace gas conversion in oceanic surface waters, a first set of incubation experiments of natural Arctic waters were performed in January 2025 at GEOMAR in Kiel, Germany. 200 litres of Arctic waters were taken in August 2024 during a research cruise on board RV Polarstern in the Fram Strait (N79° 0.02' E5° 40.1') from 10 m depth and carried back to GEOMAR after the cruise with the help of scientists responsible for Task 1.2. The water was distributed in acid-cleaned 2-litre polycarbonate incubation bottles and spiked with ship effluent (scrubber effluent). Besides a control run, 1% of open loop scrubber (treatment 1) and 1% of closed loop scrubber (treatment 2) were added. All 54 bottles were placed in a temperature-controlled water bath under natural light conditions and covered with a screen to mimic the amount of sunlight that reaches the seawater mixed layer (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Set-up of an incubation experiment

Set up located at the pier of Kiel Fjord in January 2025. Photo credit: D. Booge, GEOMAR

The experiment ran for ten days, with three bottles per treatment sacrificed for sampling once per day around local noon. Results from earlier experiments with similar volumes and incubation times did not show any evidence of bottle effects or changes in community composition. Changes in the phytoplankton and heterotrophic community composition and trace gas production were monitored throughout the experiment. In order to disentangle production and consumption processes, isotopically labelled (deuterated) trace gases (DMS-d₃, isoprene-d₅) were added to follow their loss in the treatments. All trace gas measurements were made with purge and trap gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Additional ancillary measurements (e.g. trace metals, nutrients, pH, salinity, CDOM) were undertaken to get a detailed biogeochemical overview of the influence of scrubber water within the incubations. Furthermore, pure scrubber water was tested for potential pollutants (BTEX, PAHs, PCBs, PFAS).

3.7.3 Preliminary findings

Preliminary results show highly elevated nitrate values in the closed loop scrubber effluent, which could have a fertilizing effect on the growth of phytoplankton and the consequent production of biogenic trace gases. Concentrations of pollutants were mainly below the detection limit for both the open and closed loop scrubber, except for PAH concentrations in the closed loop scrubber effluent. Phenanthrene, naphthalene and fluorene were the most abundant compounds within the group of PAHs and accounted for 58%, 14% and 10%, respectively. Benzene levels were elevated in the open loop scrubber treatments relative to the control.

3.8 Task 1.8 Stranded Marine Litter

Lead: forScience; M1–M24

3.8.1 Task overview

The task addresses marine litter pollution in south-western Spitsbergen, Svalbard. The study focuses on the north-western part of Sørkapp Land, an uninhabited area located within the South-Spitsbergen National Park,

which (due to the distribution of ocean currents) constitutes the first potential accumulation zone for marine debris transported from lower latitudes and the Barents Sea.

The work plan includes two fieldwork campaigns, each lasting approximately one month, conducted over consecutive summer seasons along the minimum of 20 continuous kilometres of highly varied coastline. All litter items visible to the naked eye within individual working sections are manually collected, categorized according to predefined criteria, and weighed. Additional data is gathered on litter distribution in relation to coast typography and exposure to phenomena occurring at sea. Once analysed, the litter is removed from the area to eliminate the immediate threat to the local ecosystem and prevent its further contamination with secondary microplastics.

The task will result in a set of quantitative, qualitative and distributional data regarding marine litter and the rate of its accumulation in the near-shore terrestrial environment of the study site. It will contribute to WP2: Risk assessment and local resilience strategies for ecosystems and communities in response to pollution and WP3: Facilitating effective science-based pollution-control governance.

3.8.2 Explanation of work carried out

The forScience team successfully organised and conducted a fieldwork campaign in north-western Sørkapp Land (Figure 12), ensuring full compliance with the requirements and restrictions associated with the area's location within the South-Spitsbergen National Park. The field team consisted of five members, and the campaign lasted for twenty-eight days (from July 6 until August 5, 2024), totalling 140 person-days.

Figure 12. Task 1.8 study area

Figure credit: A. Nawrot, Fundacja forScience. Map data: Norwegian Polar Institute

The field team manually collected all marine litter stranded within the study area (27 working sections covering the total of 36 consecutive kilometres of the coast) and, using a motorboat, transported it to the forScience field base at Palffyodden for sorting and analysis. Following analysis, the litter was transferred to the Polish Polar Station Hornsund. In late August, RV *Horyzont II* delivered the litter to the port of Longyearbyen, from where it was collected by the staff of the local waste management facility (Longyearbyen Miljøstasjon).

3.8.3 Preliminary findings

During the first fieldwork campaign, the forScience team collected and analysed marine litter stranded along 32 previously studied kilometres of the coast (Sections #1–23). Given that the amount of litter found (approximately 17 kg/km) was significantly lower than anticipated based on prior accumulation rate calculations (approximately 63 kg/km), a more thorough analysis was conducted than originally planned (see Table 3 for details). This extended analysis, referred to as the Deep Dive, involved the examination of over 4400 litter items. In the process, 198 samples of synthetic materials were taken for further analysis from litter items made of plastics, synthetic fibres and other non-natural materials that could not be easily identified either by plastic identification codes (which were absent) or by comparison to previously identified materials. The samples were delivered to the Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland, where they were subjected to a chemical analysis for further insights into polymer types.

In addition, the study area was extended by four kilometres (Sections #24–27), where litter had not been previously collected or studied. As the average amount of marine litter in these new sections was almost 400 kg/km, the analysis was conducted in line with the original plan. This involved assessing the litter's quality (material category and selected litter categories) and quantity (mass) per section of the coast.

At the time of this report, the litter data is in the process of being collated and organised.

Table 3. Type of data collected as part of the extended marine litter analysis (Deep Dive)

Scope of Analysis	Clarification	Example
Beach	Section number	#1
Abundance	Number of items	1
Mass	Total (for the specified number of items) in grams	90
Photograph	Single image of analysed litter item or set of items	
Litter category	Type of item	Packaging
Litter subcategory	Type of item within the broader litter category	Household cleaning products
Material category	General material identification based on predominant constituent material	Synthetic polymers: hard plastic
Material type	Detailed material identification within the selected category	HDPE
Material type info source	Basis for material identification	Recycling code
Brand	Based on visible brand name or logo	Unknown
Brand owner / Manufacturer	Based on information provided on the item or online search	INCO S.A.
Country of origin	By brand, GS1 company prefix or place of manufacture	Poland
Origin identification method	Type of information used to determine item nationality	Brand owner / Manufacturer
Manufacture date	As found on the item	Unknown
Expiry date	As found on the item	Unknown
Degradation level	Based on visual assessment	Moderate
Gender	Target gender of the product	Out of scope

3.9 Task 1.9 Monitoring of litter dynamics

Lead: CAU, Contributors: forScience; M1-M24

3.9.1 Task overview

This task aims to set up a tower-based monitoring scheme using remote observation stations with optical time-lapse cameras in an uninhabited site in Svalbard for time-lapse monitoring of beach dynamics and marine litter accumulation (i.e. deposition and retention). This task is carried out as part of a bigger task of CAU (under WP2) where the objective is to establish a wide network of time-lapse cameras for automated coastal litter monitoring in Iceland and Greenland using machine learning approaches.

3.9.2 Explanation of work carried out

CAU designed a tripod-mounted time-lapse camera setup for continuous monitoring of marine litter pollution in Svalbard (see Figure 13). The camera captures an image every hour and is mainly powered by solar energy, ensuring efficient and sustainable power generation, especially when light conditions are poor. The camera is mounted on a field tripod, which is anchored to the ground using tear-resistant cord and a box filled with sand and stones, providing stability with locally available materials against various environmental conditions (e.g., strong winds). To maintain functionality during periods without solar power, the camera is supported by external batteries securely stored in the anchor box.

The time-lapse camera has been successfully set up by forScience (on behalf of CAU) at a coastal site in Svalbard and an initial short time-lapse (between 22 July and 2 August 2024) measurement was collected before the forScience team left the site. The camera was installed on 22 July 2024 south of Hornsund fjord, Svalbard, as shown in Figure 14. The site selection process considered factors such as securely anchoring the tripod and choosing areas with a higher likelihood of litter accumulation. This decision was informed by past observations of litter volumes and concentration along the coast, with 127.7 kg recorded in 2019 and 117.7 kg in 2021, over our location of interest^{4, 5}. While the litter volume for 2024 was relatively lower at 39.4 kg, this location still ranked third in terms of the highest litter concentration. It's important to note that the section where these volumes were observed spans about 1.2 km, and the camera's field of view covers only a fraction of this area (information provided by Fundacja forScience, Task 1.8).

3.9.3 Preliminary findings

In summer 2025, forScience will recover the camera and the final time-lapse dataset from Svalbard. So far, no litter has been detected in the initial data from Svalbard. Development and improvement of the machine learning algorithms will commence once a sufficient amount of labelled training data has been generated. Successful training and accurate predictions from machine learning algorithms require access to a sufficient volume of well-labelled datasets for each class type.

⁴ Józwiak, B., Nawrot, A. (2019). *Report on the execution of Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup project in 2019*. Fundacja forScience. ISBN 978-83-956002-1-0. <https://forscience.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/SMLC-Report-2019.pdf>

⁵ Józwiak, B., Nawrot, A. (2021). *Report on the execution of Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup project in 2021*. Fundacja forScience. ISBN 978-83-956002-3-4. <https://forscience.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/SMLC-Report-2021.pdf>

Figure 13. Time-lapse camera in Svalbard

Field picture of the installed time-lapse camera in Svalbard (a, photo credit: A. Nawrot, Fundacja forScience) and image from the initial short time-lapse dataset (between 22 July and 2 August 2024), illustrating the field of view of the installed camera (b, photo credit: CAU)

Figure 14. Location of the time-lapse camera in Svalbard

Time-lapse camera location for year-round monitoring of accumulated marine beach litter. The camera was installed on 22 July 2024 south of Hornsund fjord, Svalbard. Figure credit: V. Lion, CAU

3.10 Task 1.10 Heavy metal contamination

Lead: forScience; M1–M24

3.10.1 Task overview

The task focuses on heavy metals, incl. mercury (Hg), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), chromium (Cr), thallium (Tl), and lead (Pb), originating from both natural and non-natural sources. These metals accumulate, among others, in the Arctic cryosphere and, due to climate change, are released to the environment and temporarily trapped in soils and freshwater bodies, such as streams and lakes.

To assess the state of Svalbard's ecosystem, the forScience team collects freshwater and soil samples from uninhabited (protected) areas in southern Svalbard (see: Task 1.8) and inhabited areas in Central Svalbard. All samples are then shipped for chemical analysis to the Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland.

3.10.2 Explanation of work carried out

During the first fieldwork campaign, the forScience team successfully collected soil and freshwater samples in inhabited areas of central Svalbard (vicinity of Longyearbyen, Figure 15a) and uninhabited areas of southern Svalbard (north-western Sørkapp Land, Figure 15b).

Figure 15. Soil and freshwater sampling spots in Svalbard

Located (a) in the vicinity of Longyearbyen, and (b) in north-western Sørkapp Land, Svalbard. Figure credit: A. Nawrot, Fundacja forScience. Map data: Norwegian Polar Institute

Soil samples were collected from areas measuring 30 cm x 30 cm (Figure 16), with two samples taken at each sampling spot: sample A from the depth of 0–2 cm, and sample B from the depth of 2–5 cm (total sample depth: 5 cm). Prior to collection, each layer (A and B) was mixed, with plants and stones removed. Using a plastic spatula, the samples were placed into polypropylene zip-lock bags and appropriately labelled. The samples were then

pre-dried at room temperature, followed by drying in a laboratory dryer at $< 40^{\circ}\text{C}$. In total, about 80 individual soil samples were collected, with 40 samples taken from each of the two regions (Figure 15).

Figure 16. Soil sampling conducted in July 2024

(a) delimitation of the sampling area; (b) layer B at the depth of 2-5 cm; (c) sample collection. Photo credit: B. Józwiak & A. Nawrot, Fundacja forScience

Freshwater samples were collected from streams and lakes in coastal areas, with each sample collected from a distinct location into two 50 ml HDPE Eppendorf tubes. On-site filtration was performed, and water parameters, including pH, conductivity, water temperature, and alkalinity, were measured (Figure 17). Samples were preserved with nitric acid (for metal analysis), and chloroform (for anions analysis). In total, 40 freshwater samples were collected during the 2024 fieldwork campaign, 19 from central Svalbard and 21 in Sørkapp Land.

Figure 17. Freshwater sampling conducted in July 2024

(a) on-site sample filtration; (b) on-site measurements of pH, conductivity and water temperature; (c) on-site alkalinity measurements. Photo credit: B. Józwiak, Fundacja forScience

All samples have been delivered to the Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland, where they will undergo chemical analyses for a range of elements, including heavy metals, using ICP MS, AAS and IC analytical methods. Additionally, soil samples will be analysed using FTIR to identify specific chemical groups, minerals, and organic matter.

3.10.3 Preliminary findings

No preliminary findings are available at this point.

3.11 Task 1.11 Integration/synthesis of results, report writing

Lead: forScience, GEOMAR; M12-M34

3.11.1 Task overview

The task involves integrating and synthesizing the results of individual WP1 tasks into a unified, comprehensive report. Due to the multidisciplinary nature of Tasks 1.1 to 1.10, active cooperation among all WP1 members will be required to compile and juxtapose individual, specialised insights, and integrate them for a joint, more thorough understanding of the complex problem that WP1 aims to address.

3.11.2 Explanation of work carried out

Data acquisition and analysis within individual WP1 tasks are ongoing. Regular meetings are held between the WP1 task teams to ensure effective coordination, alignment, and, where applicable, the production of comparable data across tasks. The process of compiling and integrating the results has not yet commenced.

3.11.3 Preliminary findings

Not applicable.